

Deliverable A3.2 - Report on Monitoring Model Definition

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Author(s)	Nicola Alessi, Nicola Riitano, Francesca Assennato, Daniela Smiraglia, Serena d'Ambrogi, Cristina Tarantino, Paolo Mazzetti, Valentina Rastelli, Vito Cambria, Marcello Vitale, Vicenç Carabassa, Cristina Domingo
Editor	Nicola Alessi, Nicola Riitano

Executive Summary

The restoration efforts within degraded sites in southern European countries have been studied and tracked by the NL4DL LIFE project using both field data that is currently available and data collected by satellite. The complexity and heterogeneity of the degradation processes among pilot sites brought to light concerns and the need for standardization and harmonization of ecological/physical indicator, particularly those obtained through satellite data, especially when used as proxies of land degradation. The project's goal has been to offer reference methods that, once the degradation processes have been identified, can be used to track how well restoration efforts based on nature-based solutions (NBS) are working on degraded lands. The procedure for medium and long-term monitoring of ecosystem restoration interventions (such as NBS) in degraded drylands, using remote sensing techniques beyond the usual typical short-term in-field campaigns, serves to assess the effectiveness of restoration activities and improve sustainable land management. The operational tool presented in this deliverable called Newlife 4 Drylands Web Tool, starting from the degradation processes, identifies sustainable solutions (NBS) along within indices/indicators related to each degradation processes to monitor the effectiveness of these solutions. Using the datasets referring to the pilot sites of the project as an experimental test, an attempt was made to connect on the basis of a reconnaissance among the experts in the field within the project, the variables at play between the identification of the degradation process, its measurement and the choice of the best restoration action, which in turn will have to be measured and monitored by the same methods, in order to ensure the effective success of restoration through nature-based solutions and the limitation, containment or stopping of the degradation phenomenon(s) affecting that area. This tool aims to reduce the knowledge effort, subjective analysis and helps in prioritizing options.

Table of Contents

1 Introduction.....	4
1.1 Aim of the task.....	4
1.2 Monitoring model rationale	5
2. Data investigation and collection	6
2.1 Degradation processes	6
2.2 Indices and Indicators.....	8
2.2.1 Remote sensing indices	12
2.2.2 Composite indices	15
2.2.3 In Situ indicators.....	17
2.3 Nature Based Solutions	21
3 Data available for Pilot sites	23
El Bruc site (Spain)	23
Tifaracas site (Spain).....	24
Alta Murgia (Italy).....	24
Palo Laziale (Italy).....	25
Asteriousia (Greece)	25
Nestos (Greece)	26
3.1 Discussion on available data.....	26
4 Expert Based Connections between Variables.....	32
5 Towards a Decision Making Support System for Drylands.....	37
5.1 Newlife4Drylands Web-tool	37
5.2 EO Browser / Copernicus.....	45
5.4 Tool examples.....	47
Conclusions.....	48
References (Unico)	50

1 Introduction

The action is focused on the definition of a monitoring model able to connect NBS and remote sensing indicators to be used as a support in decision making for adaptive management of restoration actions in drylands, improving ecosystems services provision. The ongoing or recently concluded restoration projects through NBS considered in the case studies, let available a complete assessment of the status and trend of degradation and ecosystem services on the basis of field data, to be used for the monitoring model definition. A correlation analysis between indicators and biophysical parameters from case studies is performed to identify specific conditions for monitoring.

The monitoring model definition is built upon the comparison between characteristics and solutions for drylands identified in action A1, available indicators for monitoring of status and changes from A2 and correlation with parameters and ecosystem assessment from A4. Being the correlation of remote sensing indicators to biophysical parameter an open topic in research, a limited research provided in a first phase, necessary to set the usability of indicators in different environmental conditions is devoted to identify the better and updated methodology for the correlation.

The action then is focused on setting the correlation on the basis of methodology defined and supported by a statistical analysis between the environmental parameters derived from case studies and the remote sensing indicators. ISPRA and IIA will provide the set of remote sensing indicators, IBE-CNR will contribute to develop the statistical analysis, conducted for each sampling site, and testing whether environmental parameters and remote sensing indices are different between case studies sites. Partners responsible for case studies (Sapienza, CREAM, UoC, IIA) will provide data input from the assessment of local conditions from A4.

The final part of the action will define the monitoring model for different desertification condition and restoration actions, on the basis of framework of characteristics and solutions for drylands identified in action A1. All partners provide support to the internal discussion on the model. This task will provide also the tuning with the suggestions from relevant scientific stakeholders identified in action B2 as Scientific support team.

A discussion of results on monitoring model with international stakeholders is part of final workshop foreseen in action B1. The action is developed from month 6 to the end of the project. Phases of the action and responsibility:

A.3.1 Research for NBS/desertification indicators correlation methodology (IIA+IBECNR+ISPRA)

A.3.2 Setting correlation parameters (All)

A.3.3 Definition of the monitoring model and discussion with relevant stakeholders (All) 1. Develop specific techniques to monitor failures and successes of restoration activities

2. to define a framework (A1) that will be used in the following definition of a monitoring model

3. To provide a framework and a protocol for identifying sustainable solutions that could be successfully implemented in degraded drylands e.g., restoration land activities aiming to improve vegetation cover and productivity in those areas where desertification processes are undergoing (vulnerable areas)

1.1 Aim of the task

The purpose of this task is to develop a cognitive and technical framework so as to provide, through a dedicated tool, decision making support in the restoration actions of degraded areas in arid and semi-arid zones through nature based solutions.

In the first phase, environmental datasets related to the pilot sites were collected, organized and homogenized, covering data from different sources (from remote sensing, in situ, other ancillary data). Based

on the analysis on pilot sites and the initial assessment of the most frequent methodologies for identifying drivers of land degradation and their trends and a classification of nature-based solutions a logical framework has been established.

1.2 Monitoring model rationale

The complexity of variables capable of intercepting degradation phenomena and their variability in time and space make it necessary to use support systems to analyze and read trends and the state of soil degradation. In particular, for timely action to contain degradation phenomena that may occur in protected areas of various types there is a need for tools that are capable of providing synthetic readings of complex numerical patterns.

Using the datasets referring to the pilot sites of the project as an experimental test, an attempt was made to connect on the basis of a reconnaissance among the experts in the field within the project, the variables at play between the identification of the degradation process, its measurement and the choice of the best restoration action, which in turn will have to be measured and monitored by the same methods, in order to ensure the effective success of restoration through nature-based solutions and the limitation, containment or stopping of the degradation phenomenon(s) affecting that area.

The Tool considers the three essential dimensions as the basis for navigation and the logical path of choosing the best monitoring tools: indicators, degradation processes and nature-based solutions.

- **Indicators:** Indicators are quantifiable measures that can be used to assess the state and trend of a natural or socio-ecological system. They are essential for monitoring because they provide concrete evidence of change and allow you to identify areas of concern that require action.
- **Degradation processes:** Degradation processes are the mechanisms through which natural or socio-ecological systems deteriorate. Understanding these processes is essential for developing effective mitigation and restoration strategies.
- **Nature-based solutions:** Nature-based solutions are interventions that use natural processes to solve or mitigate environmental problems. These solutions are often more effective and sustainable than technological solutions and offer additional benefits, such as biodiversity conservation and improved water and air quality.

By considering these three dimensions together in an integrated approach it is possible to guide users to the best monitoring indicators and to the selection of appropriate nature-based solution. In particular, it is possible to:

- Identify the most relevant indicators for the specific environmental condition, taking into account the degradation processes that affect it.
- Guide the users through the available sources to calculate these indicators accurately and reliably.
- Integrate monitoring data with other relevant information, such as environmental and socio-economic data, to gain a more complete understanding of the state and trends of the system.
- Explore a selection of nature-based solutions tailored to face the specific challenge

The indicators dimension helps to ensure that monitoring is focused on the most important aspects of the system. The degradation processes dimension helps to identify the underlying causes of change, which is essential for developing effective mitigation strategies. The nature-based solutions dimension helps to identify opportunities which are often more cost-effective than technological solutions to solve environmental problems.

2. Data investigation and collection

2.1 Degradation processes

Identification of degradation processes needs multidisciplinary expertise, the interoperability of which is not always easy and immediate. Although the definition of land degradation internationally follows the UNCCD guidelines for calculating SDG 15.3.1. The U.N. indicator lends itself as fundamental for cross-national comparison for the national and regional level but hardly scalable for the local level and therefore ineffective for monitoring environmental restoration actions.

Land degradation refers to the deterioration of the quality and productivity of land, resulting from various processes and human activities. Considering the study area covered by the project and the arid and semi-arid conditions of the areas involved, a set of degradation processes was selected in the initial stages of this work package.

Although the processes are multiple, often interconnected and indistinguishable from one another. In order to structure the following phases of this work, it was decided in deliverable A1.1 to schematize the processes as follows, in order to obtain groups that are as mutually exclusive as possible without neglecting important aspects concerning the different dimensions of soil and land degradation

- **Landscape Modification:** Landscape modification refers to the alteration of the natural landscape through human activities such as urbanization, land clearing, and infrastructure development. These activities can disrupt ecological processes, lead to habitat fragmentation, and result in the loss of biodiversity and ecosystem services.
- **Aridification:** Aridification is the process by which previously non-arid or semi-arid areas become increasingly dry and arid. It can occur naturally due to climate change or be exacerbated by human activities such as deforestation and unsustainable water management practices. Aridification reduces soil moisture, limits vegetation growth, and can lead to desertification.
- **Forest Fires:** Forest fires are the uncontrolled burning of forests, often caused by natural factors like lightning or human activities such as arson or accidental ignitions. While some fires play a natural role in ecosystem dynamics, frequent and intense forest fires can lead to the destruction of vegetation, loss of biodiversity, soil degradation, and increased vulnerability to erosion.
- **Hydrological Modification:** Hydrological modification refers to the alteration of natural water flows and patterns through activities like dam construction, channelization, and drainage for agriculture or urban development. These modifications can disrupt the hydrological cycle, leading to changes in groundwater recharge, altered river flows, and the loss of wetlands, affecting the health of ecosystems and contributing to land degradation.
- **Overgrazing:** Overgrazing occurs when livestock graze on vegetation excessively, beyond the capacity of the land to support them sustainably. Overgrazing leads to the removal of vegetation cover, soil compaction, erosion, and the degradation of pasturelands, resulting in reduced productivity and ecological imbalances.
- **Soil Salinization:** Soil salinization is the accumulation of salts in the soil, often caused by excessive irrigation or poor drainage. As water evaporates, salt remains in the soil, leading to increased salinity levels. Salinization negatively affects plant growth, reduces soil fertility, and can render land unsuitable for agriculture.
- **Soil Organic Matter Decline:** Soil organic matter decline refers to the loss or reduction of organic matter content in the soil. It can result from factors such as deforestation, overuse of chemical fertilizers, intensive farming practices, and improper soil management. The decline in soil organic matter affects soil structure, nutrient cycling, water-holding capacity, and overall soil health, leading to decreased productivity.
- **Soil Erosion by Water and Wind:** Soil erosion by water and wind involves the detachment and movement of soil particles due to the action of rainfall, runoff, wind, or a combination of both. It occurs when vegetation

cover is removed, and the soil becomes exposed. Soil erosion can result in the loss of fertile topsoil, decreased soil productivity, and sedimentation in water bodies, impacting both agricultural and natural ecosystems.

- **Decline in Vegetation Community Functioning:** This refers to a decrease in the overall health, diversity, and functioning of plant communities in an ecosystem. It can occur due to factors such as habitat destruction, pollution, invasive species, and climate change. A decline in vegetation community functioning disrupts ecological processes, reduces ecosystem resilience, and contributes to land degradation.

- **Decline in Vegetation Cover/Biomass:** A decline in vegetation cover/biomass refers to the reduction in the density or extent of plant growth in an area. It can result from various factors, including deforestation, overgrazing, land clearing, and climate change. Reduced vegetation cover leads to soil exposure, increased erosion, loss of habitat, and decreased ecosystem productivity.

- **Habitat Loss:** Habitat loss refers to the destruction, degradation, or fragmentation of natural habitats. It occurs primarily due to human activities such as urbanization, agriculture.

2.2 Indices and Indicators

The monitoring of degradation processes is carried out mainly using satellite monitoring and through information obtained from field surveys. The variables that can be detected and compared by both methods will be the subject of analysis and evaluation in another section of this deliverable. Monitoring land degradation processes through remote sensing indices and in situ surveys have their respective pros and cons, which can be schematized as follows in tables 1 and 2.

Remote sensing and in-situ indicators are both important tools for monitoring and assessing soil degradation. However, each approach has its own strengths and weaknesses, and using them together can provide a more complete and accurate picture of the situation.

Remote sensing has a number of advantages over in-situ monitoring. It can cover large areas quickly and easily, and it can provide data on a variety of soil properties, including land cover, vegetation, soil moisture, and soil erosion. This can be useful for identifying areas of potential soil degradation, tracking changes over time, and assessing the effectiveness of mitigation measures. However, remote sensing also has some limitations. It can be difficult to interpret remote sensing data, and it can be affected by factors such as cloud cover and atmospheric conditions. In addition, remote sensing data may not be available for all areas, especially remote or inaccessible areas. In-situ monitoring can provide more accurate and detailed data than remote sensing. It can be used to measure soil properties such as texture, structure, organic matter content, and nutrient levels. This information can be used to assess the health of the soil and identify the causes of degradation. However, in-situ monitoring also has some limitations. It can be time-consuming and expensive, and it is limited to small areas. In addition, in-situ measurements may not be representative of the entire area under study.

By combining remote sensing and in-situ monitoring, it is possible to overcome the limitations of each approach and obtain a more detailed and trustworthy representation of the conditions. Remote sensing can be used to identify areas of potential soil degradation and to track changes over time. In-situ monitoring can be used to provide more detailed information on soil properties and to assess the effectiveness of mitigation measures. Here are some specific examples of how remote sensing and in-situ monitoring can be used together to monitor and assess soil degradation:

- Remote sensing can be used to identify areas of bare soil, which are more likely to be eroded. In-situ monitoring can then be used to measure soil erosion rates in these areas.
- Remote sensing can be used to track changes in vegetation cover. In-situ monitoring can then be used to measure soil properties, such as organic matter content, in areas with different vegetation cover.
- Remote sensing can be used to identify areas of land use change. In-situ monitoring can then be used to assess the impact of these changes on soil properties.

By combining remote sensing and in-situ monitoring, it is possible to develop more effective strategies for preventing and mitigating soil degradation. Index, indicator, and composite index are all terms used to describe measurements of soil degradation and in general environmental variables. The list of indices and indicators is a product of activities A.1 and A.2, however, there are important distinctions between these terms.

Index, indicator, and composite index are all terms used to describe measurements of soil degradation. However, there are important distinctions between these terms. An index is a single measurement that summarizes a complex concept. For example, the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) is an index that measures the greenness of vegetation. NDVI can be used to track changes in vegetation cover, which is a key indicator of soil degradation. An indicator is a variable that provides information about a specific aspect of soil degradation. For example, the content of organic matter is an indicator of soil health. Organic matter

is important for soil structure, water retention, and nutrient cycling. A composite index is a combination of two or more indicators. For example, the Soil Degradation Index (SDI) is a composite index that combines indicators of soil erosion, soil fertility, and soil organic matter. SDI can be used to provide a comprehensive assessment of soil degradation. The difference between an index and an indicator is that an index is a single measurement, while an indicator is a variable. An index can be used to summarize the value of one or more indicators. The difference between an index and a composite index is that a composite index is a combination of two or more indices. A composite index can be used to provide a more comprehensive assessment of a complex concept than a single index.

Table 1 - Remote Sensing Indices pros and cons

REMOTE SENSING INDICES	
PROS	CONS
<p>Large-Scale Coverage Remote sensing allows for wide-scale coverage, providing information on land degradation processes over large areas. It enables monitoring of extensive regions, including remote or inaccessible areas, which may be challenging to survey in situ.</p>	<p>Limited Spatial Resolution Remote sensing data may have limited spatial resolution, particularly for freely available satellite imagery. Fine-scale details and localized variations may be challenging to capture, especially for small-scale land degradation processes.</p>
<p>Continuous Monitoring Remote sensing provides the ability to collect data regularly and continuously over time. It allows for the detection of temporal changes in land degradation processes and the assessment of long-term trends. Objective and Quantitative: Remote sensing indices provide objective and quantitative measurements, allowing for standardized comparisons and analysis. They provide consistent and repeatable information, enabling researchers to monitor changes consistently.</p>	<p>Indirect Measurements Remote sensing indices provide indirect measurements and proxies for land degradation processes. They rely on spectral signatures and mathematical algorithms, which may not capture all aspects or nuances of specific degradation processes accurately.</p>
<p>Rapid Assessment Remote sensing data can be processed quickly, allowing for rapid assessment and timely response to land degradation events. It supports early warning systems and helps in decision-making processes.</p>	<p>Lack of Ground Truth Validation Remote sensing data may require validation through in situ surveys or ground truthing to ensure accuracy and reliability. Without ground truthing, it can be challenging to precisely interpret remote sensing results and determine the exact causes of observed changes.</p>
<p>Integration of Multiple Data Sources Remote sensing data can be combined with other data sources, such as climate data or socioeconomic data, to analyze the drivers and impacts of land degradation comprehensively.</p>	

Table 2. In Situ and On Field Data Pros and Cons

IN SITU SURVEYS	
<i>PROS</i>	<i>CONS</i>
<p>Detailed and Localized Information</p> <p>In situ surveys provide detailed and localized information on land degradation processes. They allow for direct observations, measurements, and assessments of specific sites or areas, capturing fine-scale variations and characteristics.</p>	<p>Limited Coverage and Sampling</p> <p>In situ surveys are often limited to specific locations or sample sites due to resource constraints. They may not capture the entire extent of land degradation over large areas, potentially leading to a biased representation of the overall degradation patterns.</p>
<p>Ground Truth Validation</p> <p>In situ surveys provide ground truth data that can validate remote sensing results. They help verify the accuracy and reliability of remote sensing indices, improving the confidence in the interpreted land degradation information.</p>	<p>High Cost and Time-Intensive</p> <p>In situ surveys can be costly, time-consuming, and labor-intensive, especially when covering extensive areas or conducting long-term monitoring. They may require skilled personnel, equipment, and logistical arrangements, making them impractical for large-scale assessments.</p>
<p>Specific Process Characterization</p> <p>In situ surveys enable a detailed characterization of land degradation processes, including their drivers, impacts, and underlying factors. They provide insights into the mechanisms and dynamics of degradation, contributing to a more comprehensive understanding.</p>	<p>Subjectivity and Variability</p> <p>In situ surveys involve subjective interpretations and measurements, which can introduce variability and biases. Different observers may have varying levels of expertise, leading to inconsistencies in data collection and analysis.</p>
	<p>Difficulty in Long-Term Monitoring</p> <p>In situ surveys may face challenges in long-term monitoring, especially when it comes to maintaining consistent sampling protocols and continuity of data collection. Ensuring data consistency over time can be difficult, particularly for long-duration studies.</p>

To overcome limitations, a combination of both remote sensing indices and in situ surveys is often recommended. Integrating these approaches allows for leveraging the strengths of each method and obtaining a more comprehensive understanding of land degradation processes.

In the tool it is preferable to start a monitoring phase, without costs, via remote sensing to limit the area and understand the medium-term trends in order to identify priority areas on which to start recovery actions or in order to adopt a better sampling scheme for the surveys

2.2.1 Remote sensing indices

Remote sensing indices are important for assessing and monitoring land degradation due to several reasons, ranging from vegetational characterization to water use efficiency of different soils.

Remote sensing indices provide a quantifiable measure of vegetation health. For example, the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) compares near-infrared and red reflectance to estimate vegetation density and photosynthetic activity. By analyzing changes in NDVI values over time, it becomes possible to identify areas experiencing vegetation degradation, such as deforestation or land cover changes related to desertification. These indices, indeed, help in detecting and characterizing land cover changes, which are often indicators of land degradation. The Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI) can identify changes in water bodies, such as shrinking lakes or drying rivers, which signify degradation of aquatic ecosystems. Similarly, indices like the Normalized Difference Built-Up Index (NDBI) help in detecting urban expansion and changes in land use that contribute to land degradation.

Remote sensing indices assist in evaluating soil erosion, a significant form of land degradation. The Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation (RUSLE), a widely used model, incorporates various remote sensing indices like the Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index (SAVI) and the Modified Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index (MSAVI) to estimate soil erosion rates. These indices help identify areas at risk of erosion, enabling targeted interventions and land management practices.

They also help assess vegetation stress caused by factors like drought, pollution, or disease. For instance, the Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI) quantifies water content in vegetation, enabling the detection of water stress or drought conditions. Monitoring vegetation stress is crucial for understanding the impact of environmental factors on plant health and identifying areas where land degradation is occurring due to reduced vegetation productivity. Remote sensing indices provide a consistent and objective means to monitor land degradation trends over large areas and extended periods. By analyzing temporal changes in indices like NDVI or the Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI), it becomes possible to detect and quantify long-term degradation patterns, such as vegetation loss or degradation hotspots. These trends help inform land management strategies, conservation efforts, and policy decisions.

In summary, remote sensing indices play a vital role in assessing and monitoring land degradation by providing quantifiable measures of vegetation health, detecting land cover changes, evaluating soil erosion, assessing vegetation stress, and monitoring long-term degradation trends. Their application enables efficient and systematic monitoring of land degradation, aiding in the development of targeted interventions and sustainable land management practices.

These indices can be considered in monitoring land degradation because they provide valuable information about the condition and health of the land. Let's discuss each category of indices in more detail:

- **Vegetation Indices:** Vegetation indices, such as the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), assess the density and vigor of vegetation cover. They measure the amount of chlorophyll present in plants and indicate their overall health and productivity. Monitoring changes in vegetation indices over time can reveal degradation, such as deforestation, desertification, or the loss of plant cover due to human activities or natural factors.
- **Burned Areas Indices:** Burned areas indices, such as the Burned Area Index (BAI) or the Normalized Burn Ratio (NBR), detect and quantify the extent of burned areas following wildfires or intentional land clearing. Monitoring the occurrence and severity of wildfires provides important insights into land degradation caused by fire, including the destruction of vegetation, loss of biodiversity, and soil degradation.

- **Water Indices:** Water indices, such as the Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI), help assess the presence and quality of water resources. They indicate the abundance of water in vegetation and soil, as well as the condition of water bodies. Monitoring water indices can reveal land degradation associated with water scarcity, drought, or excessive irrigation, which can lead to soil erosion, desertification, and reduced agricultural productivity.
- **Soil Indices:** Soil indices, such as the Normalized Difference Soil Index (NDSI) or The Normalized Difference Bare Soil Index (NDBSI), provide information about percentage of bare soil exposed during a period of monitoring and in general can identify areas where soils are dominant over tree coverage. Monitoring soil indices can identify degradation processes such as soil erosion, nutrient depletion, soil sealing, or changes in soil structure, which affect agricultural productivity and ecosystem health.
- **Soil Salinity Indices:** Soil salinity indices, such as the Normalized Difference Salinity Index (NDSI), quantify the salt content in the soil. Excessive salinity can result from poor irrigation practices or natural processes like saltwater intrusion. Monitoring soil salinity indices helps identify areas where salinization is occurring, which leads to reduced agricultural productivity, vegetation loss, and ecosystem degradation.
- **Drought/Dryness Indices:** Drought and dryness indices, such as the Normalized Difference Drought Index (NDDI) or the Vegetation Condition Index (VCI), measure the moisture content of vegetation and soil. They indicate the severity and duration of drought events and can help assess the impact of climate change and human activities on water availability. Monitoring drought indices provides insights into land degradation due to water stress, reduced crop yields, and increased vulnerability of ecosystems.

By monitoring these indices over time and across different regions, land managers and policymakers can identify areas experiencing degradation, understand the underlying causes, and implement appropriate measures to mitigate and reverse land degradation processes.

To analyse degradation in the study areas, a selection of the most effective indices was made, divided into categories: Vegetation, Fire, Water, Soil, Salinity and Drought/Aridity. The information obtained in the previous deliverables was used in the construction of the tool in order to provide for each index sheet, the generic formula, the formula considering the nomenclature of the Sentinel-2 satellite bands, the references and keys to interpret each index, as well as an explanation of how the index can be used for the analysis of that particular degradation process.

Table 3. Vegetation Indices considered within the project

Type	Acronym	Description	Generic Formula	Formula by Sentinel-2 bands
Vegetation Indices	NDVI	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index	$\frac{R_{800} - R_{670}}{R_{800} + R_{670}}$	$\frac{NIR - Red}{NIR + Red}$
	GNDVI	Green Normalized Difference Vegetation Index	$\frac{R_{800} - R_{550}}{R_{800} + R_{550}}$	$\frac{NIR - Green}{NIR + Green}$
	MSAVI ₂	Modified Soil-Adjusted Vegetation Index	$\frac{2R_{800} + 1 - \sqrt{(2R_{800} + 1)^2 - 8(R_{800} - R_{670})}}{2}$	$\frac{2 * NIR + 1 - \sqrt{(2 * NIR + 1)^2 - 8 * (NIR - Red)}}{2}$
	OSAVI	Optimized Soil-Adjusted Vegetation Index	$(1 + 0.16) \frac{R_{800} - R_{670}}{R_{800} + R_{670} + 0.16}$	$(1 + 0.16) \frac{NIR - Red}{NIR + Red + 0.16}$
	NDRE	Normalized Difference RedEdge	$\frac{R_{860} - R_{700}}{R_{860} + R_{700}}$	$\frac{NIR_{narrow} - RedEdge1}{NIR_{narrow} + RedEdge1}$
	ARVI	Atmospherically Resistant Vegetation Index	$\frac{R_{900} - [R_{670} - (R_{450} - R_{670})]}{R_{900} + [R_{670} - (R_{450} - R_{670})]}$	$\frac{NIR - [Red - (Blue - Red)]}{NIR + [Red - (Blue - Red)]}$
	EVI ₂	Enhanced Vegetation Index 2	$2.5 \frac{R_{800} - R_{670}}{R_{800} + 2.4R_{670} + 1}$	$2.5 \frac{NIR - Red}{NIR + 2.4Red + 1}$
	REP	RedEdge Position	$705 + 35 \frac{(R_{670} + R_{780}) - R_{700}}{R_{740} + R_{700}}$	$705 + 35 \frac{(Red + RedEdge3) - RedEdge1}{RedEdge2 + RedEdge1}$
	PRI	Photochemical Reflectance Index	$\frac{R_{531} - R_{570}}{R_{531} + R_{570}}$	$\frac{Blue - Green}{Blue + Green}$
Burned Areas Indices	NBR	Normalized Burn Ratio	$\frac{R_{860} - R_{2200}}{R_{860} + R_{2200}}$	$\frac{NIR_{narrow} - SWIR2}{NIR_{narrow} + SWIR2}$
	NBR ₂	Normalized Burn Ratio 2	$\frac{R_{1600} - R_{2200}}{R_{1600} + R_{2200}}$	$\frac{SWIR1 - SWIR2}{SWIR1 + SWIR2}$
Water Indices	NDWI ₁	Normalized Difference Water Index 1	$\frac{R_{800} - R_{2130}}{R_{800} + R_{2130}}$	$\frac{NIR - SWIR2}{NIR + SWIR2}$
	NDWI ₂	Normalized Difference Water Index 2	$\frac{R_{550} - R_{800}}{R_{550} + R_{800}}$	$\frac{Green - NIR}{Green + NIR}$
	MNDWI	Modified Normalized Difference Water Index	$\frac{R_{550} - R_{2130}}{R_{550} + R_{2130}}$	$\frac{Green - SWIR2}{Green + SWIR2}$
Soil Indices	NDSI	Normalized Difference Soil Index	$\frac{R_{1650} - R_{560}}{R_{1650} + R_{560}}$	$\frac{SWIR1 - Green}{SWIR1 + Green}$
	NDBSI	Normalized Difference Bare Soil Index	$\frac{R_{1650} - R_{860}}{R_{1650} + R_{860} + 0.001}$	$\frac{SWIR1 - NIR_{narrow}}{SWIR1 + NIR_{narrow} + 0.001}$
	BI	Bare Index	$\frac{(R_{1650} + R_{670}) - (R_{900} + R_{450})}{(R_{1650} + R_{670}) + (R_{900} + R_{450})}$	$\frac{(SWIR1 + Red) - (NIR + Blue)}{(SWIR1 + Red) + (NIR + Blue)}$
Soil Salinity Indices	SSI ₁	Soil Salinity Index-1	$\sqrt{R_{[520:600]} * R_{[630:690]}}$	$\sqrt{Green * Red}$
	SSI ₂	Soil Salinity Index-2	$2 * R_{[520:600]} - (R_{[630:690]} + R_{[770:900]})$	$2 * Green - (Red + NIR)$
	SSI ₃	Soil Salinity Index-3	$\sqrt{R_{[630:690]}^2 + R_{[520:600]}^2}$	$\sqrt{Red^2 + Green^2}$
	SI	Salinity Index	$\frac{R_{[530:590]} * R_{[640:670]}}{R_{[450:510]}}$	$\frac{Green * Red}{Blue}$
	SASI	Soil Adjusted Salinity Index	$\frac{R_{[630:690]}}{100 * R_{[450:520]}^2}$	$\frac{Red}{100 * Blue^2}$
Drought/Dryness Indices	NDDI	Normalized Difference Drought Index	$\frac{NDVI - NDWI_1}{NDVI + NDWI_1}$	
	DSI	Desertification Soil Index	$\frac{R_{1648} - R_{498}}{R_{1648} - R_{2203} + 0.2}$	$\frac{SWIR1 - Blue}{SWIR1 - SWIR2 + 0.2}$

2.2.2 Composite indices

Although the synthetic information of a classical remote sensing index can be considered effective in providing information about the state of a particular environmental component, as seen in the previous section, the complexity of some degradation processes require the combined use of composite indices. Within this project, some of them were selected from the multitude of experiences in this topic in order to investigate the possibility of using these indices within decision-making processes related to the planning of protected areas and areas at risk of degradation/desertification.

The following composite indices have been chosen:

- SDG 15.3.1: This Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) indicator focuses on the proportion of land that is subject to degradation, including processes such as erosion, desertification, deforestation, and loss of soil quality. It aims to measure the extent of soil erosion and desertification, which are significant forms of land degradation affecting agricultural productivity, biodiversity, and ecosystem sustainability.
- SDG 15.1.2: This indicator within SDG 15 relates to the proportion of important ecosystems that are under protected areas, compared to their total area. It assesses the extent to which ecosystems of high importance for biodiversity conservation are effectively protected through designated protected areas, contributing to the preservation of biodiversity and sustainable land management.
- SDG 11.3.1: This indicator falls under SDG 11, which focuses on sustainable cities and communities. The indicator 11.3.1 specifically measures the Ratio of land consumption rate to population growth rate.
- ESAI (Environmentally Sensitive Areas to Desertification): ESAI is an acronym for Environmentally Sensitive Areas to Desertification Index. It is a composite index that assesses the vulnerability of environmentally sensitive areas to desertification. By considering indicators such as vegetation cover, soil quality, and climatic factors, ESAI helps identify areas at risk of desertification, allowing for targeted interventions and conservation efforts to prevent or mitigate land degradation caused by desertification.
- SDVI (Standardized Drought Vulnerability Index): SDVI is an index that quantifies and assesses the vulnerability of an area to drought. It combines various indicators such as precipitation, temperature, soil moisture, and vegetation health to provide a standardized measure of drought vulnerability. SDVI helps in evaluating and comparing the vulnerability of different regions to drought, enabling effective drought management strategies, resource allocation, and planning for drought-prone areas.

Table 4. Composite Indices selected within the project

Indicator	Sub-indicator	Metric/Measures	Final Formula	
SDG 15.3.1 (v2 released on March, 29th 2021)	"proportion of land that is degraded over total land area"	Land Cover (LC) change (Trend in LC)	LC Area	One Out, All Out
		Land Productivity loss	Net Primary Production (NPP)/Gross Primary Product	
		Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) decline	SOC	
		Further sub-indicators		
		Loss of habitat quality	Habitat cover Area	
		Burnt Areas	LC Area	
		Fragmentation Index	Mesh density	
		Areas of potential impact	LC Area	
		Density of artificial LC	LC Density	
		Increasing of not sealed areas	LC Area	
Indicator	Sub-indicator	Metric/Measures	Final Formula	
SDG 15.1.2	"Proportion of important sites for terrestrial and freshwater biodiversity that are covered by protected areas, by ecosystem type"	Ecosystem within protected area	$\frac{\text{Coverage of an ecosystem within protected area}}{\text{Coverage of the Key Biodiversity Areas}}$	
		Key Biodiversity Areas		
Indicator	Sub-indicator	Metric/Measures	Final Formula	
SDG 11.3.1	"ratio of land consumption rate to population growth rate"	Land Consumption Rate	$\frac{\ln(Urb_{grid,t+n} / Urb_{grid,t})}{n}$ Urb _{grid,t+n} is the surface occupied by urban areas, in the output cell considered, at the final year (t+n).....	$\frac{\text{Land Consumption Rate}}{\text{Population Growth Rate}}$
		Population Growth Rate		
Indicator	Sub-indicator	Metric/Measures	Final Formula	
ESA(I)	Environmentally Sensitive Areas to Desertification (Index)	Soil Quality Index (SQI)	$(\text{Soil Texture} * \text{Rock Fragment} * \text{Soil Depth} * \text{Parent Material} * \text{Drainage} * \text{Slope Gradient})^{1/6}$	$(SQI * CQI * VQI * MQI)^{\frac{1}{4}}$
		Climate Quality Index (CQI)	$(\text{Rainfall} * \text{Aridity Index} * \text{Slope Aspect})^{1/3}$	
		Vegetation Quality Index (VQI)	$(\text{Fire Risk} * \text{Erosion Protection} * \text{Drought Resistance} * \text{Plant Cover})^{1/4}$	
		Management Quality Index (MQI)	$(\text{Land Use Intensity} * \text{Policy})^{1/2}$	

Indicator	Sub-indicator	Metric/Measures	Final Formula
SDVI	Standardized Drought Vulnerability Index	cSPI6	$SDVI = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \text{Scaled Values of the Components}}{\text{Number of Components (N = 6)}}$
		cSPI12 (Standard Precipitations)	
		Supply	
		Demand	
		Impacts	
		Infrastructure	

It is interesting to note that some of the composite indices are the result of a mixed combination of remote sensing indices and those measured on the ground (in situ). Although, from our point of view, the use of multiple indicators would be more effective if machine learning algorithms were used in the analyses to steer the complexity of the variables and translate them into essential variables (what on the statistical side takes place in PCA, principal component analysis), the use of composite indices favours the readability of the results, facilitates comparisons between different study areas and decreases the risk that too much information leads to confusing and error-prone analyses of individual or groups of indicators.

2.2.3 In Situ indicators

The In Situ indicators list comprises various indicators used to monitor and assess land degradation. These indicators can be categorized into physical and ecological indicators, as well as socio-economic indicators. Here's a brief description of each category and some selected indicators:

Physical and Ecological Indicators:

1. **Climate:** Indicators related to climate conditions such as air temperature, rainfall, aridity index, potential evapotranspiration, rainfall seasonality, and rainfall erosivity.
2. **Water:** Indicators related to water resources, including water quality, water quantity, groundwater exploitation, and water consumption/demand.
3. **Soils:** Indicators related to soil characteristics, such as drainage, parent material, slope aspect, slope gradient, soil depth, soil texture, soil water storage capacity, organic matter content, and electrical conductivity.
4. **Vegetation:** Indicators related to vegetation cover, including major land use types, vegetation cover type, plant cover, and deforested areas.
5. **Water Runoff:** Indicators related to water runoff, such as drainage density, flooding frequency, and impervious surface area.
6. **Fires:** Indicators related to fire occurrence and its impact, including fire frequency, fire risk, and burned area.

Socio-economic Indicators:

1. **Agriculture:** Indicators related to agricultural practices and outcomes, such as farm ownership, farm size, land fragmentation, net farm income, and parallel employment.
2. **Cultivation:** Indicators related to cultivation practices, including tillage operations, tillage depth, tillage direction, and mechanization index.
3. **Husbandry:** Indicators related to animal husbandry practices, such as grazing control and grazing intensity.
4. **Land Management:** Indicators related to land management practices, including fire protection, sustainable farming, reclamation of affected and mining areas, soil erosion control measures, soil water conservation measures, and the presence of terracing.

5. Land Use: Indicators related to land use patterns, such as land abandonment, land use intensity, land use type, period of current land use, and distance from the seashore.
6. Water Use: Indicators related to water resource management, including aquifer over-exploitation, irrigation percentage of arable land, runoff water storage, water consumption by sector, and water scarcity.
7. Tourism: Indicators related to tourism activities, such as tourism intensity and tourism change.
8. Social: Indicators related to social factors, including human poverty index, old age index, population density, population growth rate, and population distribution.
9. Institutional: Indicators related to institutional factors, including farm subsidies, protected areas, and policy implementation.

The complete list of in situ indicators is as follows, organized by thematic groups (e.g. Physical and ecological indicators) and subgroups (e.g. Climate).

PHYSICAL AND ECOLOGICAL INDICATORS

CLIMATE

Air temperature

Rainfall

Aridity Index

Potential evapotranspiration

Rainfall seasonality

Rainfall erosivity

WATER

Water quality

Water quantity

Groundwater exploitation

Water consumption/demand

SOILS

Drainage

Parent material

Rock fragments

Slope aspect

Slope gradient

Soil depth

Soil texture

Soil water storage capacity

Exposure of rock outcrops

Organic matter surface horizon

Electrical conductivity

VEGETATION

Major Land use

Vegetation cover type

Plant cover

Deforested areas

WATER RUNOFF

Drainage density

Flooding frequency

Impervious surface area

FIRES

Fire frequency

Fire risk

Burned area

SOCIO-ECONOMIC INDICATORS

AGRICULTURE

Farm ownership

Farm size

Land fragmentation

Net farm income

Parallel employment

CULTIVATION

Tillage operations

Tillage depth

Tillage direction

Mechanization index

HUSBANDRY

Grazing control

Grazing intensity

LAND MANAGEMENT

Fire protection

Sustainable farming

Reclamation of affected areas

Reclamation of mining areas

Soil erosion control measures

Soil water conservation measures

Terracing (presence of)

LAND USE

Land abandonment

Land use intensity

Land use type

Period of current land use

Distance from seashore

WATER USE

Aquifer over exploitation

Irrigation percentage of arable land

Runoff water storage

Water consumption by sector

Water scarcity

TOURISM

Tourism intensity

Tourism change

SOCIAL

Human poverty index
Old age index
Population density
Population growth rate
Population distribution

INSTITUTIONAL

Farm subsidies
Protected areas
Policy implementation

These indicators are used to assess the state of land degradation and provide valuable information for monitoring and decision-making processes to promote sustainable land management and conservation. This type of indicators need information on the ground, available through sampling, surveys and field measurements. Although they are time and cost expensive, they are fundamental and complementary to remote sensing indicators as they represent ground truth and the most detailed data available, both in temporal and spatial terms. However, covering large portions of the territory is difficult, both because of the sample size sometimes required to align with exhaustive statistical reliability and because of the difficulty in reaching certain sampling points. In addition, the frequency of updating amplifies the costs and time required for subsequent processing. The choice of effective sampling schemes and suitable update frequency represents a crucial node in the application of any monitoring and degradation assessment model.

2.3 Nature Based Solutions

Nature-based solutions (NBSs) are characterized as "Solutions that are cost-effective, simultaneously provide environmental, social, and economic benefits, and help build resilience." NBSs are inspired by and supported by nature. Through locally tailored, resource-effective, and systemic interventions, these solutions increase and diversify the amount of nature and natural features and processes in cities, landscapes, and seascapes¹. NBSs offer a solution to the environmental and societal problems that climate change and other pressures have made worse. The phrase "nature-based solutions" first appeared in the late 2000s (MacKinnon et al. 2008; Mittermeier et al. 2008) in reference to the search for novel approaches to mitigate and adapt to the effects of climate change while also preserving biodiversity and enhancing sustainable livelihoods. NBS was mentioned by the IUCN in a position paper for the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (IUCN, Dudley et al., 2009), the phrase was swiftly adopted by policy, which saw NBS as a creative way to spur economic growth and job creation as part of a green economy. In the context of its Horizon 2020 Framework Programme (EC2015), the European Commission is now formulating an EU research and innovation policy on NBS with the goal of establishing Europe as a global leader in this area.

Nature-based solutions (NBS) relate to the sustainable management and use of nature for addressing societal difficulties. Examples of NBS include greening roofs or walls to cool off urban areas during the summer, to absorb storm water, to abate pollution, to promote human well-being while boosting biodiversity, and to abate climate change. NBS integrates science, policy, and practice and produces biodiversity benefits in the

¹ (https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/research-area/environment/nature-based-solutions_en)

form of diversified, well-managed ecosystems, building on and completing existing biodiversity conservation and management measures (Eggermont, 2015).

This list consists of various nature-based solutions aimed at ecological restoration, habitat restoration, ecological protection, and soil and water bioengineering. Here's a brief description of each category and some selected solutions:

Ecological Restoration (Functional and/or Structural), these solutions involve, for example:

- Habitat Restoration
- Selective shrub trimming: This involves trimming shrubs selectively to create suitable conditions for standing freshwater habitats.
- Ex situ plant reproduction and reintroduction: It refers to reproducing and reintroducing plants in a controlled environment before returning them to their natural habitats.
- Selective removal of alien and invasive plant species: This solution focuses on removing non-native plant species that have a negative impact on the ecosystem, such as *Amorpha fruticosa*.

Ecological Protection: refers to a set of measures and actions aimed at safeguarding ecosystems and preserving their integrity. It involves strategies and practices that mitigate threats and minimize negative impacts on natural habitats, species, and ecological processes.

Protected areas: Establishing protected areas to conserve and protect ecosystems and biodiversity.

Land exclosures: Implementing land exclosures through fencing to limit disturbance factors like overgrazing and wild boar rooting.

Reserves, conservancies: Setting up reserves and conservancies to safeguard natural areas and wildlife.

Natural Systems Agriculture: is an approach to farming that seeks to mimic and integrate natural processes and principles into agricultural systems. It aims to enhance sustainability, biodiversity, and ecosystem services while promoting productive and resilient agricultural practices. The core idea behind Natural Systems Agriculture is to work in harmony with nature rather than against it.

Agro-ecology: Applying ecological principles to agricultural systems, focusing on sustainable farming practices and biodiversity conservation.

Organic farming: Cultivating crops without the use of synthetic pesticides and fertilizers, promoting soil health and biodiversity.

Agroforestry: Integrating trees or shrubs with agricultural crops, providing multiple benefits such as improved soil quality, biodiversity, and climate resilience.

Soil and Water Bioengineering:

- Installation of rainwater collection and distribution systems: Setting up systems to collect and distribute rainwater, promoting water conservation and management.
- Trapping sediment with vegetational measures: Using vegetation to capture and retain sediment, preventing erosion and improving water quality.

Green Infrastructures: refer to a network of natural and semi-natural areas that are strategically planned, designed, and managed to provide a range of environmental, social, and economic benefits. These green

spaces are integrated into urban and rural landscapes to enhance ecosystem services, improve resilience to climate change, and support human well-being.

- **Green infrastructure, i.e., hydraulic irrigation system:** Implementing irrigation systems that use natural elements and processes to distribute water efficiently.

Afforestation of former grasslands: Planting trees in previously grassland areas to restore forests and increase biodiversity.

Constructed wetlands: Creating artificial wetland systems to mimic natural wetland functions and provide ecosystem services.

These nature-based solutions aim to restore ecosystems, protect natural areas, promote sustainable agriculture, and implement measures for soil and water conservation. By adopting these approaches, land degradation can be monitored and mitigated while enhancing ecological resilience and sustainable land management practices.

3 Data available for Pilot sites

To develop monitoring procedures for the performance of Nature Based Solutions applied in the context of land degradation and desertification, the project focused on six European case studies in areas affected by ecosystem degradation. The areas were selected among those in which restoration activities are implemented in the context of other LIFE + and existing projects or are candidate for restoration. For the assessment of techniques to be used in the monitoring procedure, it is needed a detailed evaluation of available environmental data, field and remotely sensed observations. Here, we present a detailed description of the selected areas and available data sets divided in thematic categories - i.e., boundaries, environmental maps, field observations, remotely sensed data.

El Bruc site (Spain)

The counties of Anoia and Bages experienced serious fire events in 1986 and 2015. In the latter event burned 1,235 ha of forest, dominated by *Pinus halepensis*, located in the municipalities of El Bruc, Òdena, Castellfollit del Boix, Sant Salvador de Guardiola and Castellolí. Since pines species do not propagate by vegetative reproduction, modest and variable regeneration throughout the area has been observed, especially in the years immediately after the fire. Thus, in the framework of the LIFE Green Link project (LIFE15 CCA / SE / 125), more than 20 ha of forest and agricultural species have been planted to recover the most degraded areas and favour the recovery of the agro-silvopastoral mosaic. Thus, a proper monitoring approach should observe and measure vitality of planted seeds, seedlings or saplings to find a relationship with remotely sensed images. The available data on this site are:

Boundaries: administrative boundaries of municipalities, El Bruc site and protected areas are provided as spatial polygons.

Environmental maps: elevation (spatial resolution at 5 m and 30 m), climate Standardised Precipitation-Evapotranspiration Index (spatial resolution at 100 m), geology (spatial scale at 1:50 000), landscape (spatial scale at 1:75 000), lithology (spatial scale at 1:250 000), soil maps (spatial scale at 1:250 000), land cover maps, hydrology and habitat types are provided as spatial polygons, or spatial grid in the case of elevation; evapotranspiration categorical map is provided as spatial polygons; a map of wildfire occurrences is provided as spatial polygons ranging from 1986 to 2020.

Field observations: vegetation structure has been sampled on three sites using two time windows (2017 and 2019) and other ten different sites (2018) where both woody and herbaceous species total cover and medium height were measured; plant biomass has been measured in six individuals for three woody species (*Olea*

europaea, *Quercus ilex*, *Quercus faginea*) for a total of 18 measurements at different sites; cocoon degradation, seedling vigour (categorical) and both diameter and height variations from 2017 to 2019 have been measured for 12 species with different sampling efforts (from 28 to 376 individuals) according different treatments, for a total of 1688 samples, biodiversity has been measured in four sites collecting occurrences and abundances for 132 species; wild fauna occurrences has been measured in seven sites using footprints, excrements and nest as proxy of occurrence; root lengths and weights have been measured for three species at four sites; soil data has been sampled at four sites and at two soil depths where structural and chemical compositions were measured.

Remotely sensed data: Drought, soil, soil salinity, vegetation and water indices based on Sentinel 2 images for 2017 and 2019 were provided as raster files.

Tifaracas site (Spain)

Tifaracas is located in the municipality of Artenara on the island of Gran Canaria, within the El Nublo Rural Park, which in turn forms part of the Gran Canaria Biosphere Reserve. It is classified as a Site of Community Interest (SCI) and Special Area of Conservation (SAC). The area is severely affected by desertification processes, which are aggravated by reduced rainfall, recurrent forest fires and herbivores, and in particular the abundant presence of feral goats. A low cover of arid and semi-arid vegetation types occurs in the area. To reverse the desertification process and improve the ecological connectivity of the adjacent Canary Island pine forests, 4000 seedlings of native forest species, trees and shrubs have been planted with the “Cocoon” system within the framework of the LIFE Green Link project (LIFE15 CCA / SE / 125). The available data on this site are:

- Boundaries: administrative boundaries of municipalities, islands, Tifaracas site and protected areas are provided as spatial polygons.
- Environmental maps: elevation (spatial resolution at 25 m), geology (spatial scale at 1:50 000), land cover maps, hydrology and habitat types are provided as spatial polygons, or spatial grid in the case of elevation; map of wildfire occurrences is provided as spatial polygon.
- Field observations: vegetation structure has been sampled on 40 transects of 25 m long where both woody and herbaceous species total percentage cover estimate each 20 cm; plant biomass has been measured for two woody species (*Pistacia atlantica*, *Pinus canariensis*) for a total of eight individuals at different sites; cocoon degradation, seedling vigour (categorical) and both diameter and height variations from 2017 to 2019 have been measured for four species with different sampling efforts (from 256 to 584 individuals) according different treatments, for a total of 1204 samples, biodiversity has been measured in four sites collecting occurrences and abundances for 13 species; wild fauna occurrences has been measured in two sites using footprints, excrements and nest as proxy of occurrence; root lengths and weights have been measured for one species at four sites; soil data has been sampled at three sites and at two soil depths where structural and chemical compositions were measured.
- Remotely sensed data: Drought, soil, soil salinity, vegetation and water indices based on Sentinel 2 images for 2016 were provided as raster files.

Alta Murgia (Italy)

Alta Murgia is in Southern Italy and is classified as a Site of Community Interest and Special Protection Area (IT9120007). The area has been included in a National Park since 2004. It is characterized a typical Mediterranean agro-pastoral landscape occupied by semi-natural rocky dry grasslands that are traditionally used as extensive pastures. The Alta Murgia semi-natural grassland ecosystem hosts numerous endemic, rare or trans-Adriatic distribution species. In Alta Murgia, accelerated processes of habitat degradation, fragmentation and biotic contamination of local biodiversity (i.e., woody encroachment) due to both

agricultural intensification (transformation of grassland pastures because of agricultural cereal crop intensification) and land abandonment. Furthermore, long-term below-average rainfall (climate change), an increase in either legal and illegal mining activities or wind farm infrastructures, fire events and the spread of invasive species have contributed to threaten the ecosystem, which is in danger of being destroyed. The available data on this site are:

- Boundaries: administrative boundaries of protected areas are provided as spatial polygons;
- Environmental maps: land use maps for 2006 and 2011 are provided as spatial polygons;
- Remotely sensed data: Grassland total cover and phenology for 2018 at 10 m of spatial resolution was provided as raster files.

Palo Laziale (Italy)

The Palo Laziale forest (Roma, Lazio) represents a residual floodplain forest which in the past stretched over the entire coastline of central-western Italy. It forms the core of the Natura 2000 site 'Bosco di Palo Laziale' (SCI IT6030022) covering about 50 ha and is dominated by the 'Pannonian-Balkan turkey oak-sessile oak-forest' (91M0) type of habitat, where species-rich transient-freshwater habitat types occur – i.e., the 'Mediterranean temporary ponds' (*3170). Since 1995, an increasing exposition to soil aridity and extreme drought events have led to a dramatic case of forest degradation and dieback in Palo Laziale. In 2003, a tremendous summer heatwave caused the death of about 40% of the adult trees. Subsequently, a concurrent pathogenic attack of the fungus *Biscogniauxia mediterranea* increasing the degree of forest degradation. In 2015, about 80% of the initial forest canopy was lost. To face these environmental threats, a set of solutions of restoration ecology were conceived from that multidisciplinary study and started to be implemented when the LIFE PRIMED project was approved. The available data on this site are:

- Boundaries: administrative boundary map of the site is provided as spatial polygons;
- Environmental maps: habitat map derived from vegetation sampling is provided as spatial polygons;
- Remotely sensed data: Drought, soil, soil salinity, vegetation and water indices based on Sentinel 2 and Pleiades images for January and July 2020 were provided as raster files, a time-series ranging from 2002 to 2021 of Pleiades images was provided for a selection of remotely sensed indicators, high resolution raster of phenology is provided.

Asteriousia (Greece)

The Asterousia mountain range has been inhabited and managed by human populations since ancient times. The relatively low vegetation cover that is typical of the south-east Mediterranean, coupled with long dry summers and strong winter rainfalls that are intensified by current climatic deregulation and multidimensional human pressures, have led to an elevated risk of land degradation and desertification. The abandonment of traditional land cultivation, the expansion of road networks and infrastructure serving tourism development and RES projects, the overgrazing of virtually all of the grasslands due to the steep increase in livestock and the abandonment of a traditional extensive animal farming model, driven by the current CAP subsidies policy have been identified as the main land use changes leading to a degradation of productive arable land, a decline in vegetation cover, loss of biodiversity and the functioning. The available data on this site are:

- Boundaries: administrative boundary map of the site is provided as spatial polygons;
- Environmental maps: elevation, aspect and slope provided at 20 m of spatial resolution; land-cover maps (2000, 2005, 2010, 2017, 2021) at 10 m of resolution as spatial resolution were provided as raster files;

- Remotely sensed data: satellite-based indices of soil salinity were provided for 2017 and 2021 at 10m of resolution.

Nestos (Greece)

The Nestos River and its delta, in north-eastern Greece, forms delta, covers an area of 55,000 ha. On account of its size and the variety of its habitats, the delta is considered among the most important wetlands of Greece and Europe. A significant feature of SCI GR1150010 is the riparian forest, which is a priority habitat according to EU Directive 92/43 and is one of the largest of its type in Mediterranean. The river is the most important water resource in its region and has been the subject of bilateral negotiations for many years. The main land uses consist of parks and protected fauna/flora areas, but also skiing, forestry, grazing, hydroelectricity, urban settlements and scattered industries, fish farming and tourism. Pollution and no sustainable management of water resources, large-scale hydraulic infrastructures along the river, Extensive agricultural activities pose a threat to the area.

- Environmental maps: land-cover maps (2000, 2005, 2010, 2017, 2021) at 10 m of resolution as spatial resolution were provided as raster files;

- Remotely sensed data: satellite-based indices of soil salinity were provided for 2017 and 2021 at 10m of resolution. Hydroperiod indices were provided as raster files at 10 m of spatial resolution for three temporal windows ranging from 2017 to 2021.

3.1 Discussion on available data

To monitor failures and success of restoration activities using a remotely sensed approach, appropriate and suitable field observations on soil and soil cover are needed. These observations should represent measurements of the soil and/or vegetation conditions over space and/or time. Due to the diversity of disturbance agents affecting natural ecosystems, specific observations might be collected at different sites – e.g., occurrence of an alien plant species, plant photosynthetic activity, plant vigour of planted saplings, etc. In addition to the typology of observations, the spatio-temporal scale is a fundamental aspect of field data, considering the interest in evaluating statistical relationships with remotely sensed images. The spatio-temporal scale should indeed coincide between field and remotely sensed data. Thus, plant species covering one square meter or less should be monitored using high resolution images. Likewise, the acquisition date of satellite images should coincide with the collection of field data, depending on the life cycle of the studied organism. For example, tree species could be analysed using satellite images acquired before or after the year when field data was collected assuming that tree species are more stable and persistent with respect to an annual herbaceous species. These considerations will be critically evaluated in regard to data previously collected in the pilot sites of the project.

A set of heterogeneous information are available in the six study cases. While environmental data resulted to be suitable only for a general characterization of the studied sites, remotely sensed images and derivatives such as vegetation or soil indices are optimal proxies to monitor ecosystem conditions. In detail, Sentinel 2 products were provided as main environmental indices for vegetation, soil, water, salinity and drought conditions. Only in one site, Palo Laziale, very high resolution images are available from the Pleiades products. In contrast, the field observation recording levels of land degradation and desertification resulted to be scanty. Moreover, the available field observations respond to different spatial scales with respect to remotely sensed indices of Sentinel 2. In detail, observations on plant species used in restoration actions in the sites (e.g., in El Bruc and Tifaracas) need high resolution images to be detected using remote sensing techniques.

Differently, both high resolution images and field observations characterizing soil are available for Palo Laziale.

Among the methodologies highlighted by the bibliographical collection reported on the Deliverable A.3.1, we selected the Pearson correlation coefficient to investigate relationships among field and Earth observations in Palo Laziale site. This analysis was conducted in order to identify the best remotely sensed indices capable of detecting measurements and features of interest observed in the field. The aim was to evaluate the strength of a linear relationship between field measurements and the corresponding spectral signal recorded by remotely sensors. A high absolute value of the Pearson correlation approximating the value of one would suggest a good correspondence between the field measurement and the spectral signal observed by remote sensors. On the contrary, a value approximating the value of zero would suggest a weak relationship between the two types of observations. The analysis was conducted on data collected at Palo Laziale site between 2018 and 2019, where 20 accurate field observations of soil structure and composition are available (see Table 10 of Deliverable A.3.1). The corresponding spectral signal of the field observations was extracted from images acquired by remotely sensed sensors at two different spatial resolutions: Sentinel 2 at 10 m of resolution and Pleiades at 2 m of resolution. To include the seasonal variability in the analysis, winter (January 2020) and summer (July 2020) images were collected from both the sensors. Furthermore, assuming that soil maintains its structure and composition in the proximity of the sampling site, for each field observation we extracted the spectral signal within a window of 9 pixels. For each of the obtained pixel spectral signal, different remotely sensed indices were obtained (see Table 10 of Deliverable A.3.1) and grouped – e.g., vegetation indices, soil indices, water indices, etc. To avoid collinearity among the 44 calculated remotely sensed indices, we conducted a Variation of Inflation Factor (VIF) with a threshold of 10 and thus retaining only indices which resulted not correlated with others. The VIF was performed separately for each group of indices and resulting indices were selected for further analyses (Table 1). The soil parameter selected (and corresponding code) for the correlation analysis are: sand average (SAND), silt average (SILT), clay average (CLAY), pH (H₂O) 10g and 25ml (pH), percentage of organic matter (OM), percentage of large sand size (2-0,5 mm; SAND1), percentage of medium size sand (0,5-0,25 mm; SAND2), percentage of small size sand (0,25-0,053 mm; SAND3), percentage of total sand (SAND4), percentage of silt (0,052-0,003 mm; SILT), percentage of clay (<0,003 mm; CLAY1), cation exchange capacity (meq/100g; CEC), electrical conductivity (μ S/cm; EC1), electrical conductivity (mS/cm; EC2), percentage of CaCO₃ (CaCO₃), percentage of soluble salts (SoS), exchangeable bases (cmol/kg) of Ca (Ca), Mg (Mg), Na (Na) and K (K), sum of bases (σ).

Code	Indices	Sentinel 2		Pleiades	
		January 2020	July 2020	January 2020	July 2020
Vegetation indices					
NDVI	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index	0	0	1	1
NDMI	Normalized Difference Moisture Index	1	1	NA	NA
GNDVI	Green Normalized Difference Vegetation Index	1	1	1	1
MSAVI2	Modified Soil-Adjusted Vegetation Index	0	0	1	1
OSAVI	Optimized Soil-Adjusted Vegetation Index	0	0	1	1
NDRE	Normalized Difference RedEdge	0	0	NA	NA
ARVI	Atmospherically Resistant Vegetation Index	1	1	1	1
EVI2	Enhanced Vegetation Index 2	0	0	1	1
REP	RedEdge Position	1	1	NA	NA
PRI	Photochemical Reflectance Index	0	0	NA	NA
Water indices					
NDWI1	Normalized Difference Water Index 1	0	0	NA	NA
NDWI2	Normalized Difference Water Index 2	1	0	1	1
MNDWI	Modified Normalized Difference Water Index	1	0	NA	NA
Soil indices					
NDSI	Normalized Difference Soil Index	1	1	NA	NA
NDBSI	Normalized Difference Bare Soil Index	1	1	NA	NA
BI	Bare Index	1	1	NA	NA
Soil salinity indices					
SSI1	Soil Salinity Index 1	0	0	1	1
SSI2	Soil Salinity Index 2	1	1	1	1
SSI3	Soil Salinity Index 3	1	0	1	1
SI	Salinity Index	0	1	1	1
SASI	Soil Adjusted Salinity Index	1	1	1	1
Drought/Dryness indices					
NDDI	Normalized Difference Drought Index	1	1	NA	NA
DSI	Desertification Soil Index	1	1	NA	NA

Table 5. List of remotely sensed indices derived from Sentinel 2 and Pleiades images acquired in January and July 2020. Selected indices by the Variation of Inflation Factor are identified with 1. In case remotely sensed indices were not calculated because of missing bands (i.e., in Pleiades images), the index is identified by NA.

	Soil salinity indices					
	SASI (Jan)	SSI2 (Jan)	SSI3 (Jan)	SASI (Jul)	SI (Jul)	SSI2 (Jul)
sand	0,17	-0,31	-0,10	-0,01	-0,11	0,15
silt	0,06	0,07	-0,09	0,01	-0,23	-0,37
clay	-0,27	0,28	0,22	0,01	0,40	0,26
ph	-0,14	-0,22	0,19	-0,31	0,43	-0,39
om	0,25	0,11	0,11	0,36	-0,28	0,27
sand1	-0,36	-0,15	0,10	-0,07	0,58	0,27
sand2	0,11	-0,13	-0,14	0,09	-0,13	0,17
sand3	0,34	-0,16	-0,06	0,08	-0,38	0,18
sand4	0,19	-0,21	-0,08	0,08	-0,16	0,27
silt1	0,08	0,08	-0,13	-0,01	-0,25	-0,38
clay1	-0,33	0,14	0,28	-0,08	0,53	0,19
cec	-0,28	0,43	0,08	0,13	0,45	0,36
ec1	0,05	-0,02	-0,10	0,35	-0,09	-0,06
ec2	0,05	-0,02	-0,10	0,35	-0,09	-0,06
caco3	0,03	0,20	-0,52	0,10	-0,36	-0,04
sos	-0,02	0,34	-0,18	-0,29	0,14	0,18
ca	-0,06	-0,44	-0,25	-0,02	0,08	-0,18
mg	0,02	0,15	-0,25	-0,14	0,03	-0,26
na	-0,18	0,33	-0,17	-0,03	0,13	-0,01
k	0,03	-0,21	0,11	0,12	0,04	-0,18
σb	-0,06	-0,33	-0,28	-0,05	0,09	-0,22

	Soil indices					
	BI (Jan)	NDBSI (Jan)	NDSI (Jan)	BI (Jul)	NDBSI (Jul)	NDSI (Jul)
sand	-0,18	-0,12	0,17	0,20	0,35	0,30
silt	-0,11	-0,13	-0,18	-0,53	-0,53	-0,24
clay	0,35	0,30	0,01	0,39	0,21	-0,07
ph	0,16	0,21	0,36	0,38	0,41	0,38
om	-0,02	-0,05	-0,21	-0,20	-0,11	-0,10
sand1	-0,18	-0,08	-0,32	0,40	0,35	-0,40
sand2	-0,09	-0,05	0,11	0,12	0,23	0,20
sand3	-0,06	-0,12	0,24	0,02	0,15	0,40
sand4	-0,13	-0,13	0,13	0,18	0,31	0,26
silt1	-0,10	-0,13	-0,11	-0,52	-0,52	-0,21
clay1	0,29	0,32	0,00	0,50	0,34	-0,02
cec	0,30	0,18	-0,11	0,40	0,28	-0,18
ec1	-0,30	-0,41	-0,38	-0,33	-0,33	-0,27
ec2	-0,30	-0,41	-0,38	-0,33	-0,33	-0,27
caco3	-0,05	-0,33	0,21	-0,38	-0,37	-0,06
sos	0,21	0,17	0,09	0,13	0,19	-0,20
ca	-0,59	-0,49	-0,23	-0,21	-0,10	-0,33
mg	0,13	-0,04	0,34	-0,10	-0,08	0,05
na	0,14	-0,01	0,03	-0,03	-0,07	-0,17
k	-0,06	-0,05	-0,02	-0,06	-0,07	0,03
σb	-0,47	-0,43	-0,12	-0,20	-0,11	-0,28

Table 6. Pearson's correlation coefficients calculated for soil structural and compositional observations against remotely sensed indices for soil salinity based on Sentinel 2 images acquired in 2020.

Table 7. Pearson's correlation coefficients calculated for soil structural and compositional observations against remotely sensed indices for soil based on Sentinel 2 images acquired in 2020.

	Drought indices			
	DSI (Jan)	NDDI (Jan)	DSI (Jul)	NDDI (Jul)
sand	-0,01	-0,13	-0,07	0,20
silt	-0,17	-0,17	-0,14	-0,38
clay	0,21	0,36	0,25	0,21
ph	0,06	0,15	0,28	0,36
om	0,06	-0,14	-0,16	-0,12
sand1	-0,02	-0,01	0,48	0,35
sand2	0,04	0,00	-0,09	0,07
sand3	0,02	-0,15	-0,31	0,03
sand4	0,03	-0,10	-0,12	0,15
silt1	-0,15	-0,14	-0,13	-0,36
clay1	0,17	0,31	0,33	0,32
cec	0,09	0,30	0,40	0,25
ec1	-0,36	-0,40	-0,01	-0,29
ec2	-0,36	-0,40	-0,01	-0,29
caco3	-0,19	0,03	-0,29	-0,41
sos	0,07	0,20	0,04	-0,02
ca	-0,43	-0,49	0,06	-0,17
mg	-0,07	0,15	-0,07	-0,15
na	-0,08	0,15	0,13	-0,08
k	0,00	0,00	-0,03	-0,07
σb	-0,39	-0,37	0,05	-0,18

	Water indices			
	MNDWI (Jan)	NDWI2 (Jan)	MNDWI (Jul)	NDWI2 (Jul)
sand	-0,08	-0,32	-0,20	0,01
silt	0,21	0,01	0,32	-0,35
clay	-0,16	0,37	-0,13	0,39
ph	-0,28	-0,11	-0,49	0,09
om	0,13	0,10	0,22	-0,09
sand1	0,27	0,08	0,04	0,65
sand2	-0,08	-0,15	-0,11	0,00
sand3	-0,17	-0,28	-0,15	-0,22
sand4	-0,08	-0,24	-0,14	0,03
silt1	0,15	-0,03	0,28	-0,37
clay1	-0,11	0,32	-0,22	0,47
cec	-0,05	0,43	-0,09	0,47
ec1	0,43	-0,09	0,28	-0,15
ec2	0,43	-0,09	0,28	-0,15
caco3	-0,13	-0,19	0,19	-0,33
sos	-0,17	0,18	0,09	0,23
ca	0,41	-0,47	0,27	0,02
mg	-0,27	-0,13	-0,02	-0,16
na	-0,08	0,13	0,05	0,07
k	0,07	-0,07	0,01	-0,11
σb	0,29	-0,42	0,23	-0,01

Table 8. Pearson's correlation coefficients calculated for soil structural and compositional observations against remotely sensed indices for water based on Sentinel 2 images acquired in 2020.

Table 9. Pearson's correlation coefficients calculated for soil structural and compositional observations against remotely sensed indices for drought based on Sentinel 2 images acquired in 2020.

	Vegetation indices							
	ARVI (Jan)	GNDVI (Jan)	NDMI (Jan)	REP (Jan)	ARVI (Jul)	GNDVI (Jul)	NDMI (Jul)	REP (Jul)
sand	0,12	0,32	0,12	0,28	0,06	-0,01	-0,35	-0,15
silt	0,07	-0,01	0,13	-0,05	0,38	0,35	0,53	0,31
clay	-0,22	-0,37	-0,30	-0,26	-0,52	-0,39	-0,21	-0,19
ph	-0,06	0,11	-0,21	-0,09	-0,34	-0,09	-0,41	-0,24
om	-0,17	-0,10	0,05	-0,07	0,31	0,09	0,11	0,12
sand1	0,20	-0,08	0,08	-0,10	-0,50	-0,65	-0,35	-0,54
sand2	0,07	0,15	0,05	0,27	0,02	0,00	-0,23	-0,04
sand3	-0,05	0,28	0,12	0,28	0,28	0,22	-0,15	0,17
sand4	0,05	0,24	0,13	0,29	0,06	-0,03	-0,31	-0,05
silt1	0,09	0,03	0,13	-0,10	0,39	0,37	0,52	0,30
clay1	-0,18	-0,32	-0,32	-0,21	-0,61	-0,47	-0,34	-0,35
cec	-0,20	-0,43	-0,18	-0,07	-0,59	-0,47	-0,28	-0,11
ec1	0,16	0,09	0,41	0,11	0,11	0,15	0,33	0,09
ec2	0,16	0,09	0,41	0,11	0,11	0,15	0,33	0,09
caco3	0,19	0,19	0,33	0,48	0,25	0,33	0,37	0,55
sos	-0,06	-0,18	-0,17	-0,27	-0,20	-0,23	-0,19	-0,11
ca	0,56	0,47	0,49	0,11	0,08	-0,02	0,10	-0,22
mg	0,05	0,13	0,04	0,15	-0,06	0,16	0,08	0,26
na	-0,01	-0,13	0,01	0,01	-0,19	-0,07	0,07	0,18
k	0,03	0,07	0,05	0,17	-0,06	0,11	0,07	0,01
σb	0,49	0,42	0,43	0,13	0,04	0,01	0,11	-0,12

	Soil salinity indices					
	SASI (Jan)	SSI2 (Jan)	SSI3 (Jan)	SASI (Jul)	SSI2 (Jul)	SSI3 (Jul)
sand	0,06	-0,34	-0,10	0,27	0,16	-0,04
silt	-0,06	0,13	0,11	-0,26	-0,44	-0,06
clay	-0,01	0,24	-0,01	-0,01	0,33	0,11
ph	0,35	-0,06	0,05	0,08	0,07	0,30
om	0,11	0,10	0,15	-0,06	-0,05	-0,23
sand1	0,27	-0,15	0,05	-0,02	0,14	0,25
sand2	-0,08	-0,17	-0,25	0,22	0,10	-0,11
sand3	-0,06	-0,21	0,01	0,28	0,23	-0,12
sand4	-0,01	-0,26	-0,11	0,29	0,24	-0,07
silt1	-0,07	0,16	0,07	-0,26	-0,45	-0,07
clay1	0,11	0,10	0,03	0,01	0,32	0,17
cec	-0,12	0,34	-0,18	0,10	0,39	0,36
ec1	-0,22	-0,10	0,06	-0,17	-0,10	0,21
ec2	-0,22	-0,10	0,06	-0,17	-0,10	0,21
caco3	-0,39	0,15	-0,35	0,04	0,11	-0,17
sos	-0,23	0,15	-0,43	0,19	0,29	0,23
ca	0,12	-0,13	-0,01	-0,13	-0,22	0,19
mg	-0,13	0,19	-0,07	-0,05	0,01	0,09
na	-0,20	0,19	-0,02	-0,23	0,01	0,08
k	-0,02	-0,07	0,04	0,20	0,10	0,14
σb	0,06	-0,06	-0,02	-0,14	-0,18	0,19

Table 10. Pearson's correlation coefficients calculated for soil structural and compositional observations against remotely sensed indices for vegetation based on Sentinel 2 images acquired in 2020.

Table 11. Pearson's correlation coefficients calculated for soil structural and compositional observations against remotely sensed indices for soil salinity based on Pleiades images acquired in 2020.

	Vegetation indices					Water indices	
	ARVI (Jan)	GNDIVI (Jan)	ARVI (Jul)	MSAVI (Jul)		NDWI2 (Jan)	NDWI2 (Jul)
sand	0,30	0,32	-0,07	-0,16	sand	-0,32	0,03
silt	-0,15	-0,15	0,25	0,43	silt	0,15	-0,32
clay	-0,17	-0,19	-0,22	-0,31	clay	0,19	0,34
ph	-0,15	0,04	-0,28	-0,16	ph	-0,04	0,24
om	-0,19	-0,07	0,24	0,10	om	0,07	-0,26
sand1	-0,04	0,11	-0,26	-0,17	sand1	-0,11	0,31
sand2	0,28	0,20	0,00	-0,10	sand2	-0,20	-0,04
sand3	0,22	0,20	0,00	-0,21	sand3	-0,20	0,00
sand4	0,28	0,26	-0,07	-0,23	sand4	-0,26	0,06
silt1	-0,14	-0,16	0,26	0,43	silt1	0,16	-0,34
clay1	-0,14	-0,09	-0,27	-0,32	clay1	0,09	0,38
cec	-0,17	-0,35	-0,43	-0,45	cec	0,35	0,50
ec1	0,17	0,08	-0,08	0,04	ec1	-0,08	0,06
ec2	0,17	0,08	-0,08	0,04	ec2	-0,08	0,06
caco3	0,26	-0,16	0,13	-0,04	caco3	0,16	-0,06
sos	0,28	-0,06	-0,28	-0,31	sos	0,06	0,32
ca	0,08	0,10	-0,04	0,17	ca	-0,10	0,01
mg	-0,04	-0,19	-0,07	-0,03	mg	0,19	0,09
na	-0,07	-0,21	-0,04	-0,02	na	0,21	0,09
k	0,04	0,05	-0,23	-0,13	k	-0,05	0,22
σb	0,06	0,03	-0,05	0,14	σb	-0,03	0,04

Table 12. Pearson's correlation coefficients calculated for soil structural and compositional observations against remotely sensed indices for water based on Pleiades images acquired in 2020.

Table 9. Pearson's correlation coefficients calculated for soil structural and compositional observations against remotely sensed indices for water based on Pleiades images acquired in 2020.

The results report weak correlations between soil and satellite observations, both at 2 m and 10 m of spatial resolution.

4 Expert Based Connections between Variables

Given the difficulty in extracting information from site-specific statistical correlations to generalize the connections between the variables that make up the monitoring workflow, an expert based solution has been developed in this action. This solution can make the same connections viable to be used in a more schematic framework, in order to support the creation of a broader structure, involving the main variables and keeping track of the interactions between them. The experts, participants of NL4DL in this and other tasks were surveyed to receive information on potential connections, having the task of connecting the three previously mentioned dimensions, defining the degree of connection: as potentially connectable or relevant. Potentially connectable in case the link is possible but not so frequent, according to their point of view, relevant in case the link is already consolidated and robust both in literature and in practice.

Starting from the results of A1 – Setting the frame for desertification, degradation processes and the most feasible and reliable Nature Based Solutions have been described and collected on the basis of literature. Indicators adopted to assess land degradation and desertification, with a particular emphasis on the processes in place at the pilot sites, have been selected and identified as relevant or not for each of the

degradation processes occurring in the pilot sites by the technical group of NewLife 4 Drylands including the scientific advisory board.

Relevant group of indicators, according to the DESIRE (a five-year EU project ended in 2012) approach, as already described in the A1.1 Report on Framework of the target degradation processes are listed in the following Tables 10 (Physical and ecological indicators) and 11 (Socio-Economic aspects).

Physical and ecological indicators	Aridification	Forest fires	Overgrazing	Soil erosion by water and wind	Soil organic matter decline	Soil salinization
CLIMATE						
Air temperature	X	X	X	X	X	X
Rainfall	X	X	X		X	X
Aridity Index	X	X	X		X	X
Potential evapotranspiration	X	X	X	X	X	X
Rainfall seasonality	X	X	X	X	X	X
Rainfall erosivity	X	X	X	X	X	
WATER						
Water quality	X					X
Water quantity	X					X
Groundwater exploitation	X					X
Water consumption/demand	X					X
SOILS						
Drainage					X	X
Parent material			X	X	X	X
Rock fragments	X		X	X		
Slope aspect	X	X	X	X		
Slope gradient	X		X	X		
Soil depth	X	X	X	X		X
Soil texture	X		X	X	X	X
Soil water storage capacity	X		X	X		X
Exposure of rock outcrops			X	X		
Organic matter surface horizon	X		X	X	X	
Electrical conductivity	X		X	X		X
VEGETATION						
Major Land use	X	X	X	X	X	
Vegetation cover type	X	X	X	X	X	
Plant cover	X	X	X	X	X	
Deforested areas	X	X	X		X	
WATER RUNOFF						
Drainage density				X		
Flooding frequency						X
Impervious surface area				X		
FIRES						
Fire frequency	X	X	X		X	
Fire risk	X	X	X			
Burned area		X	X	X		

Table 13. Physical and ecological indicators connection with main land degradation processes

To effectively establish connections between degradation processes and climatic, water, soil, vegetation, runoff, and fire indicators, it is important to have a good understanding of the underlying mechanisms of each process. This includes understanding the factors that drive each process, as well as the feedback loops that can occur between different processes. Once you have a good understanding of the underlying mechanisms, you can start to look for patterns in the data. For example, you might look for correlations between changes in climatic indicators and changes in degradation processes. You might also look for correlations between changes in different degradation processes. It is important to use multiple data sources to build a strong case for the connections between degradation processes and indicators. This includes using data from different scales, such as local, regional, and global. It is also important to use data from different sources, such as satellite imagery, ground measurements, and modeling.

Socio-economic indicators	Aridification	Forest fires	Overgrazing	Soil erosion by water and wind	Soil organic matter decline	Soil salinization
AGRICULTURE						
Farm ownership		X	X	X		X
Farm size	X		X	X	X	
Land fragmentation			X	X		
Net farm income		X	X	X		
Parallel employment			X	X		
CULTIVATION						
Tillage operations				X	X	
Tillage depth				X	X	
Tillage direction				X		
Mechanization index						
HUSBANDRY						
Grazing control	X	X	X	X		
Grazing intensity	X	X	X	X	X	
LAND MANAGEMENT						
Fire protection			X	X	X	
Sustainable farming	X			X	X	
Reclamation of affected areas						X
Reclamation of mining areas		X		X		
Soil erosion control measures	X	X	X	X	X	
Soil water conservation measures	X		X	X	X	
Terracing (presence of)	X		X	X	X	
LAND USE						
Land abandonment		X		X	X	
Land use intensity	X	X		X	X	
Land use type	X	X		X	X	X
Period of current land use				X		X
Distance from seashore						X
Landscape change (area)						
WATER USE						
Aquifer over exploitation	X					X
Irrigation percentage of arable land	X			X		X
Run off water storage	X		X	X		
Water consumption by sector	X					
Water scarcity	X	X				X
TOURISM						
Tourism intensity		X		X		X
Tourism change		X				
SOCIAL						
Human poverty index		X				
Old age index			X	X		
Population density		X	X	X		X
Population growth rate			X	X		
Population distribution						
INSTITUTIONAL						
Farm subsidies			X	X	X	
Protected areas		X	X			
Policy implementation			X	X	X	X

Table 14. Socio-economic indicators connection with main land degradation processes

NBS

The NBS concept is increasingly being referred to in scientific literature (e.g., [Kabisch et al., 2016](#); [Raymond et al., 2017a](#); [Keesstra et al., 2018](#)). One reason for its wide adoption is that the concept of nature providing solutions is simple in construct and logical for non-specialist understanding. This has encouraged its uptake in policy, practice and by the private sector ([Nesshöver et al., 2017](#)), and facilitates opportunities to bring together diverse sectors and stakeholders ([Van Ham and Klimmek, 2017](#)). Nevertheless, there is a risk that NBS will remain a vague term, without operational rigor.

In the following table the intersections between nature based solutions and the main degradation processes, for each site the connections between the most relevant dimensions were requested in order to then obtain a summary structure that can be managed in the tool. It was necessary to view only some of the processes to make the table readable, please refer to the tables attached to this deliverable for complete consultation (same goes for other cross tables in this chapter).

Table 15. Nature Based Solutions and Degradation Processes combination

NATURE BASED SOLUTIONS	Subgroup	<i>Aridification</i>	<i>Forest fires</i>	<i>Overgrazing</i>	<i>Soil organic matter decline</i>	<i>Soil erosion by water and wind</i>	<i>Decline in vegetation cover/biomass</i>	<i>Increase in invasive species</i>	<i>Trees encroachment</i>
Ecological restoration (functional and/or structural), Habitat Restoration		✓		✓		✓	✓	✓	✓
Subgroup of Nature Based Solutions falling under: Ecological Restoration	Sowing/transferring of dry plant material (e.g., dry hay, seed-enriched hay, shrub seeds)								
	Topsoil processing of degraded surfaces (e.g., harrowing, topsoil inversion, sod cutting, soil compression)	✓			✓	✓			
	Selective removal of alien and invasive plant species			✓	✓		✓	✓	✓
	Ex-situ plant reproduction and reintroduction	✓		✓	✓				
	NBS under the group of Ecological Restoration to be added								
Ecological protection		✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Subgroup of Nature Based Solutions falling under: Ecological Protection	Limiting soil disturbance factors (e.g. landslides, overgrazing, wild boar rooting)	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓		✓
	Promoting balanced agri-pastoral practices (e.g., mowing, grazing)			✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	Quitting agricultural practices	✓			✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	NBS under the group of Ecological Protection to be added								
Protected areas							✓	✓	
Land exclosures							✓	✓	✓
Reserves, conservancies							✓	✓	✓

Natural systems agriculture					✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Agro-ecology					✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Organic farming					✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Agro-forestry			✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Evolutionary-orientated forestry			✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Ecosystem-based management			✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Ecosystem-based fire management strategies			✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Managed rewilding		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Trapping sediment with vegetational measures		✓			✓	✓			
Soil and water bioengineering		✓				✓			
Water and forest management plan		✓	✓			✓			
Green infrastructures		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Green infrastructure, i.e. hydraulic irrigation system		✓		✓	✓	✓			
Afforestation of former grasslands		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓			
Constructed wetlands		✓							
Bush trimming and creation of firebreak paths			✓						
Forest habitat conservation					✓		✓	✓	✓
Phytosanitary cutting			✓				✓	✓	✓
Forestry nursery and afforestation		✓			✓	✓	✓		✓
Fire management strategies/seedling irrigation (Cocoon)			✓						
Land exclosures/seedling irrigation (Cocoon)		✓			✓	✓			
reestablishment of landscape features (i.e. stone walls) and afforestation of degraded slopes with native tree species		✓			✓	✓			

5 Towards a Decision-Making Support System for Drylands

5.1 Newlife4Drylands Web-tool

The web tool is designed to guide the manager or planner of protected areas, once the degradation process has manifested itself, to choose, among many alternatives, the strategy to monitor the evolution of the process if it is still in progress and its impacts and the effectiveness of the actions taken, with solutions based on nature, using the indicators and indices that best interpret the conditions and variations of the phenomena of interest.

A concise and exhaustive schematization of degradation processes, covering the most recurrent degradation processes in the Mediterranean area, allows for the creation of a scheme of connections, expert based with the main remote sensing and in situ indicators useful for monitoring the state and trends of soil and vegetation health in the areas concerned. A tool can help protected area managers and planners in taking the right decisions, understanding which of the categories of land degradation processes need to be prioritized. This can be done by matching the potential solutions in monitoring with the considered factors such as the severity of the problem, the rate of progression and the potential impacts on biodiversity and human communities.

It is also important to monitor the effectiveness of the management plans and make adjustments as needed. The tool can help the protected area managers to develop monitoring protocols and to analyze the results of the monitoring data.

Below are some examples of how the model can be useful, once the current degradation process has been defined.

- If the protected area is facing a problem with soil erosion, you can help the managers to develop a soil conservation plan. This plan might include measures such as planting cover crops, reducing tillage, and building terraces.
- If the protected area is facing a problem with deforestation, you can help the managers to develop a forest management plan. This plan might include measures such as replanting trees, controlling invasive species, and managing logging in a sustainable way.

The web tool, elaborated and proposed by NL4DL project and designed to be a decision-support tool for planners, managers, and maintainers of protected areas, is accessible via web link and open to other users. The navigable contents can in fact be used by students, stakeholders, professionals, or anyone that for various reasons has interest in monitoring degradation processes in natural areas.

The tool was created using a hierarchical table schema in json format, which was then adapted into html to customise the graphical interface and increase readability and clarity.

The initial Landing Page (Figure 1), is accessible from any device via browser, provides an overview and instructions on how to proceed further.

[Newlife 4 Drylands Web tool](#)

Users can chose to start from a degradation process (fig. 2) and are prompted to select a specific process that is relevant to their region or area of interest. Taking into account a list, as complete as possible, of degradation phenomena, without leaving out minor processes, a categorization is provided, incorporating them into broader categories of degradation processes. Processes have been selected among the one occurring in a representative sample of all eventualities, the one constituted by the project pilot areas.

**New Life 4 Drylands
Decision Support Web Tool**

Decision Support Web Tool

This tool is designed to guide end users through the planning of degraded site monitoring and restoration activities, monitoring indications come from case studies and general indications come from literature, it can be useful to evaluate the available Nature Base Solutions that fit for the end users case, as well as for monitoring restoration and interventions tailored for each degradation process

New Life for Drylands

NewLife4Drylands aims to provide, by using Remote Sensing techniques, a framework and a protocol for identifying sustainable solutions that could be successfully implemented in degraded lands and define mid- and long-term monitoring of interventions in desertified lands, to better evaluate restoration effectiveness and improve sustainable soil management.

Click the button below and navigate through the degradation process and their indicators and nature-based solutions available.

Click here for a list of Degradation Processes

Home Page

Land Degradation Process

Nature Based Solutions (list)

Remote Sensing Indices (list)

In Situ and Other Indicators

Logos: Institute of Atmospheric Pollution Research, National Research Council of Italy, Institute of BioEconomy, Department of Ecology, Agriculture and Food Science, Natural History Museum of Crete, University of Crete, Dipartimento di Biologia Ambientale, Hellenic Society for the Protection of Nature, CREA, ISPRA, SAPIENZA UNIVERSITÀ DI ROMA.

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Figure 1. Web tool landing page and side menu to navigate through List of Degradation Processes, Indices and Nature-Based Solutions, available at:
<https://sites.google.com/view/newlifefordrylands/home-page>

The tool may provide different options for users to navigate through the available content, allowing them to explore various aspects of degradation processes and monitoring techniques, as an example, e.g. in the page shown in fig.3 users can pick a single group of remote sensing indicators.

There is no single navigation direction (e.g.: Degradation -> Indicators -> NBS), but the user is left the possibility of exploring the various sections without them being blocked. However, the protocol indicates a degradation process as an initial element, which can also be identified on the basis of pressures (e.g. fires, droughts, floods). After selecting a degradation process, the tool will display tabs on remote sensing indicators, in situ and other indicators and nature-based solutions that can be adopted to monitor, assess and address degradation phenomena.

The web tool is a valuable resource for planners, managers, and maintainers of protected areas, is easy to navigate into and provides a comprehensive overview of degradation processes and monitoring techniques.

Some indicators are more effective for monitoring certain environmental variables than others but having a wider availability of techniques can help shed more light on the process. The tool was conceived as usable with sentinel satellite images, open and available from 2016 onwards, as far as in situ indicators are concerned, due to the extreme specificity, separate speeches would be needed for each theme. The satellite view is usually the quickest and cheapest choice for a rough indication of the state of degradation

of the area in question. The best way to determine the effectiveness of an individual remote sensing indicator is to test it in the field, ~~in other task of this projects some attempts will be done.~~

In figure 2 for example the sheet referring to the remote sensing indices considered suitable, after a participatory discussion with the expert among partners for the degradation phenomena linked to groundwater recharge. These are 3 indicators able to provide a satellite assessment of the state of soil moisture, each with different characteristics depending on the soils to be considered with instructions for use, references and some illustrated examples of indicator mapping.

- Aridification
- Change in groundwater level / quality
- Decline in vegetation community functioning
- Decline in vegetation cover/biomass
- Habitat loss
- Hydrological modification
- Increase in invasive species
- Increase in weeds
- Landscape modification
- Overgrazing
- Soil erosion by water and wind
- Soil organic matter decline
- Soil Salinization
- Soil surface compaction
- Trees encroachment

Figure 2. (On the left) In the main menu users will be asked to select a degradation process occurring in their region/area.

Figure 3. (Bottom) Example of Remote sensing indicator suited for the selected degradation process, in this case Ground Water Recharge Issues.

Remote Sensing Indices for Change in groundwater level/quality

- NDWI1 - Normalized Difference Water Index 1
- NDWI2 - Normalized Difference Water Index 2
- MNDWI - Modified Normalized Difference Water Index

Selecting a process will take the user to a tab with the information needed to understand the phenomenon from a monitoring point of view, its implications that need to be monitored and an exhaustive list of the impacts that could be involved in the manifestation of that phenomenon and that should not be underestimated.

Change in groundwater level/quality

The availability of groundwater as a water source depends largely upon surface and subsurface geology as well as climate. The porosity and permeability of a geologic formation control its ability to hold and transmit water.

The projected increase of groundwater levels will influence the soil-water balance and could potentially change the vegetation. In case of increased rooting depth and/or a vegetation with higher transpiration rates, this could potentially result in lower groundwater levels.

Groundwater occurs almost everywhere beneath the land surface. The availability of groundwater as a water source depends largely upon surface and subsurface geology as well as climate. The porosity and permeability of a geologic formation control its ability to hold and transmit water. Porosity is measured as a ratio of voids to the total volume of rock material and is usually described as a percentage. Unconsolidated sands and gravels make some of the most productive aquifers because they have many internal voids (porosity) that are well-connected.

Change in groundwater level is considered a land degradation process because it can have significant adverse effects on the overall health and productivity of the land. Here are a few reasons why:

- **Depletion of water resources:** Excessive extraction of groundwater can lead to a decline in the water table, which is the level below which the ground is saturated with water. When the groundwater level drops, it becomes harder to access water for various purposes such as drinking, irrigation, and industrial use. This depletion of water resources can result in water scarcity, affecting both human activities and ecosystems.
- **Ecological impacts:** Groundwater plays a crucial role in sustaining ecosystems by providing water to streams, rivers, wetlands, and other natural habitats. When the groundwater level declines, it can negatively impact these ecosystems. Reduced groundwater levels may lead to the drying up of streams and wetlands, which disrupts the habitat of various plant and animal species. It can also result in the loss of biodiversity and disrupt the balance of ecosystems.
- **Land subsidence:** Groundwater extraction, particularly when done excessively and without proper management, can cause land subsidence. When water is withdrawn from underground aquifers faster than it is replenished, the soil compacts and settles, resulting in the sinking or subsiding of the land surface. Land subsidence can damage infrastructure such as buildings, roads, and pipelines, and it can also affect the stability of the land, leading to increased erosion and reduced soil quality.
- **Saltwater intrusion:** In coastal areas, excessive groundwater extraction can lead to saltwater intrusion. When the groundwater level drops, it creates a pressure imbalance that allows saline water from the ocean to infiltrate into the freshwater aquifers. Saltwater intrusion can contaminate drinking water sources, rendering them unsuitable for human consumption and agricultural use. It can also harm the vegetation and agricultural productivity in affected areas.
- **Groundwater-dependent agriculture:** In many regions, groundwater is a critical source of irrigation for agriculture. When the groundwater level declines, farmers may face difficulties in accessing water for irrigation, which can lead to reduced crop yields or even crop failure. This can have significant economic implications for agricultural communities and can contribute to land degradation by reducing soil fertility and productivity.

It is important to manage groundwater resources sustainably by implementing measures such as water conservation, improved irrigation techniques, and monitoring of groundwater levels to mitigate the negative impacts of changing groundwater levels and prevent further land degradation.

References:

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Vandaele, S. J., Wilmer, T. C., and Senagala, M. S. 2005. *Water and the Environment*, p. 22-25. Published by the American Geosciences Institute Environmental Awareness Series.

Check the solutions to research, assess and restore land degradation in your area of interest

Remote Sensing Indicators

In situ and other indicators

Nature Based Solutions

Figure 4. Example of Degradation Process Description Page

Check the solutions to monitor, assess and restore land degradation in your area of interest

Remote Sensing Indices

In situ and other indicators

Nature Based Solution

Figure 5. Another Example of Degradation Process Tab and a zoom on dedicated buttons for each process

An example of a tab is shown with the indicator BI – Bare Index, the formulas for calculating the index are shown, both in sentinel and generic notation with reference to the central wavelength, should one wish to use satellite images from different sources (e.g. commercial).. In the text, there are some tips on how to use the indicator and a comparison with other indicators of the same type in the case of multiple alternatives of the same type which were discussed with partners in order to give an opinion on the effectiveness of individual remote sensing indicators.

BI – Bare Index

Bare Index or Bare Soil Index (BSI) are a numerical indicators that combines blue, red, near infrared and short wave infrared spectral bands to capture soil variations. These spectral bands are rather used in a normalized manner than their simple formula. The short wave infrared and the red spectral bands are used to quantify the soil mineral composition, while the blue and the near infrared spectral bands are used to enhance the presence of vegetation

- Formula of BSI = $\frac{(Red-Blue) - (NIR-Blue)}{(Red+Blue) + (NIR-Blue)}$
- BSI (index 0) = $\frac{(B5 + B2) - (B4 + B3 + B1)}{(B5 + B2) + (B4 + B3 + B1)}$
- BSI (index 4) = $\frac{(B5 + B3) - (B4 + B1) + (B2 + B1)}{(B5 + B3) + (B4 + B1) + (B2 + B1)}$
- BSI (index 2) = $\frac{(B11 + B4) - (B8 + B2) + (B11 + B4)}{(B11 + B4) + (B8 + B2) + (B11 + B4)}$

Generic Formula (R is the reflectance at the wavelengths (nm) denoted by the subscripts):

$$\frac{(R_{1650} + R_{670}) - (R_{800} + R_{450})}{(R_{1650} + R_{670}) + (R_{800} + R_{450})}$$

Formula by Sentinel-2 bands:

$$\frac{(SWIR1 + Red) - (NIR + Blue)}{(SWIR1 + Red) + (NIR + Blue)}$$

References:

Loi, Duong & Chou, Tien-Yin & Fang, Yao-Min. (2017). Integration of GIS and Remote Sensing for Evaluating Forest Canopy Density Index in Thai Nguyen Province, Vietnam. International Journal of Environmental Science and Development. 8. 539-542. 10.18176/ijesd.2017.8.8.1012.

Figure 6. Example of a Remote Sensing Indicator tab

From each page it is possible to return to the reference pages for the selected process and explore the other variables. Once all the information on the indicators available for that process has been collected, the nature base solutions dedicated for that process can be selected, also filtered only for that process. particular process and assuming that the remote sensing indices and in situ indicators are able to monitor the effectiveness of the restoration actions by measuring their impact on the initial state of degradation assessed. The restoration solutions are in order, from the most extensive (in terms of size and surface area involved) up to the detailed ones for which the actions consist of limited actions.

Nature Based Solutions for Aridification

Figure 7. Example of a list of adoptable Nature Based Solutions for a selected degradation process (Aridification in this case)

For in situ indicators, the tool contains a list of possible indicators with which it is possible to monitor the state of degradation of an area and evaluate its trend over time. For a technical description, please refer to future developments of the tool. Potentially each in situ indicator can lead to a page of guidelines on how to evaluate that variable or perform a search in institutional or sector databases to obtain

evaluations already carried out for that specific parameter.

In situ and other indicators for Trees Encroachment

In situ and other Indicator for Trees Encroachment

VEGETATION

Major Land use

Vegetation cover type

Plant cover

Deforested areas

SDG 15.3.1 "proportion of land that is degraded over total land area"

Land Cover (LC) change (Trend in LC)

Figure 8. Example of In situ and other indicators which can be used to monitor, assess and tackle the selected degradation process

5.2 EO Browser / Copernicus

In the remote sensing indices section, a direct connection has been inserted with a Copernicus tool, called EO Browser, for which a user manual is also provided. This other web tool allows the calculation of remote sensing indicators on satellite images of the Sentinel constellation for all available time intervals (from 2016 onwards for Sentinel 2) with global coverage, without prejudice to the limit of cloud cover for some passages. The indicators can be inserted via a simple algebraic formula of bands for which the formulas are contained in the individual tabs of this tool or with scripts for more complex formulations for which there are in any case ready-made repositories on the COPERNICUS website or for which they will be integrated directly from the NL4DL tool so as to be immediately calculable for the study areas.

Figure 9. Algebra equation between bands to calculate index.

In the first example you are calculating the NDVI for the selected area (you need to choose images or a series of satellite images without cloud cover for your area of interest and in the desired time interval). The tool facilitates the selection of the bands by suggesting the central frequency of the band (as suggested in the remote sensing indicator sheets) and the name of the band (e.g. Near Infrared, Near Red, Red).

Generic Formula

$$\frac{R_{860} - R_{2200}}{R_{860} + R_{2200}}$$

Formula by Sentinel-2 bands

$$\frac{NIR_{NARROW} - SWIR2}{NIR_{NARROW} + SWIR2}$$

References:

- Keeley, J. E. (2009). Fire intensity, fire severity and burn severity: A brief review and suggested usage. *International Journal of Wildland Fire*, 18(1), 116–126. Van Wageningen, J. W., Root, R. R., & Key, C. H. (2004). Comparison of AVIRIS and Landsat ETM+ detection capabilities for burn severity. *Remote sensing of environment*, 92(3), 397-408.

Figure 10. Example of direct button with pre-filled script to calculate complex index

If scripts are needed for more complex formulas or simply to customize the display, scripts will be made available for each indicator in order to facilitate the decision maker in viewing the variable on the place of interest

Figure 11. Example of NBR calculation for an area north of Rome (Viterbo province)

Subsequently, through a registration procedure on the Copernicus system, necessary for access to the services and the download of all the satellite data it makes available, the download of the image will be available.

The raster with the calculation result is made available but also other forms of visualization and the decomposed bands in raw form. The format can be selected from the most common (e.g. Tiff or Kmz) with spectral depth selectable based on needs and the number of combinations available in the map. The resolution and the coordinate system also allow us to carry out, on the other hand, a coordinate resampling and projection process that would otherwise require time and resources, in this way the output product can be read by any GIS software to carry out spatial or simply exported in JPEG format to be included in documentation supporting recovery activities.

Figure 12. Downloading Products from EO Browser

5.4 Tool examples

AN EXAMPLE OF USING THE WEB TOOL: ARIDIFICATION

A manager of a protected area can effectively address a soil degradation process such as aridification through a comprehensive approach that combines remote sensing indices and in-situ measurements, ultimately leading to the implementation of nature-based solutions, Here's the step he/she might take.

1. Identification of the process through biophysical evidence of the degradation. The evidence can be the increase of frequency of bare soil exposed during the year or the loss of vegetation cover in the area of interest.

2. Remote Sensing and In-Situ indicators selection to evaluate the state and monitoring the evolution of aridification in the area.

Bare soil monitoring can be effectively performed through "NDBSI - Normalized Difference Bare Soil Index" which is in the list of remote sensing indices. High values from this indices will identify bare soils in the area,

from a diachronic assessment of this index a change in the state of soil can help to identify the vulnerable area. From the suggested in situ indicators Aridity index and Rainfall data can provide a medium-term vision of the phenomenon in the area, distinguishing historically bare soil areas from more recent ones. This step can be divided into two phases:

2.1 Data Analysis:

Process and analyze the data gathered from both remote sensing and in-situ measurements. This step involves the use of specialized software and algorithms to extract meaningful information, such as trends in soil moisture, changes in vegetation, and identifying areas prone to aridification.

2.2 Identify Vulnerable Areas:

Based on the analysis, identify specific areas within the protected zone that are most vulnerable to soil degradation and aridification. This might involve the development of vulnerability maps.

3. Nature-Based Solutions:

Design and implement nature-based solutions tailored to the identified vulnerable areas. Nature-based solutions could include reforestation, afforestation, wetland restoration, or soil conservation techniques like contour farming. These solutions aim to restore ecosystem functions and enhance soil health naturally.

The manager can choose the manager chooses according to his or her context (e.g. no agricultural activity and impossibility of afforestation given the climate regime) to use the “reestablishment of landscape features”. In particular Stone walls and Windbreaks can act as physical barriers that reduce the speed of water runoff and control soil erosion. When placed strategically on slopes, they intercept rainwater, allowing it to infiltrate into the soil rather than carrying away valuable topsoil. Wind can erode topsoil and damage vegetation by removing moisture and causing physical damage. Stone walls can also act as barriers that reduce the wind's intensity, protecting the soil and plants from wind erosion. This helps prevent soil erosion, which is a major contributor to land degradation.

Once the solutions have been put in place to address the degradation process, the manager/planner can reuse the tool to address a secondary or parallel problem, or even use the same monitoring approach to verify the effectiveness of the solutions adopted.

Conclusions

The Mediterranean region presents unique environmental and soil challenges, and specific concerns for climate and ecology. Specific issues related to soil mapping and management of land degradation in the Mediterranean context need to be addressed, taking into account the specific challenges of main degradation phenomena and related indicators, together with those related to the natura based solutions available to contrast land degradation and desertification.

The NewLife4Drylands project is a pioneering initiative aimed at addressing soil degradation and combating the alarming rise of desertification through the implementation of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) and a monitoring scheme supported by remote sensing. With a primary focus on vulnerable protected areas experiencing ongoing degradation processes, the project developed.

The aim of the tool is to provide a reference procedure to be applied to monitor restoration activities based on nature-based solutions on degraded lands, once the degradation processes has been identified. Variables considered in the tool include processes of degradation, physical indicators derived from remotely sensed approaches and most common practices of nature-based solutions. Connections between these variables, which form the basis of the relational map of the tool, have been initially collected through the internal knowledge of the project and will be further deepened through expert-based questionnaires to experts of different disciplines in the field of soil and environmental sciences.

The decision-making tool provide a workflow to guide the end users in the field of environmental management and planning, through the identification of land degradation processes, the selection of monitoring indicators viable and the most suitable nature based solution for that particular degraded land. The tool will be used as an input base for an action protocol at local and regional scale for environmental management and planning

The Decision support web tool is based on a comprehensive framework for the assessment and identification of sustainable solutions in degraded drylands. The project places a strong emphasis on developing specific techniques to monitor phenomena and effectiveness of restoration activities. This monitoring aspect and the role of remote sensing is crucial for understanding the impact of interventions and refining strategies over time.

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